

EU MIGRATION AND INTEGRATION POLICY: REGULATIONS, PLANS AND BORDER CHALLENGES

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POLICY STATEMENT

The migratory flows, a phenomenon that has occurred since the beginning of humanity, have increased significantly in the last decade due to the refugee crisis. While the migrant moves to another country by choice, having as one of his/her purposes the search for better living conditions, the refugee moves because of a direct threat linked to situations of violence such as wars and political and religious conflicts. Although many of them leave their countries with the expectation of returning to their places of origin after the end of the conflicts, the time spent as a refugee can exceed twenty years. Therefore, it is important to have a migration, asylum, and integration policy, based on human rights, that assures to the migrant and the refugee the right to be welcomed and included in the chosen destination to safeguard their existence. This is still the challenge for several countries, especially for countries that are part of the European Union and are still in the process of consolidating their territory after the liberalization of internal borders.

BACKGROUND

European history is characterized by rivalries, revanchism and conflicts whose international treaties were not able to contain since the countries, deprived of full sovereignty, sought largely individual gains. Peace and the balance of power within Europe came, according to Leite (4), when the states considered interdependence as a path to international cooperation for the harmonization of interests and mutual gains, overflowing the economic integration movement to other strategic sectors.

The long process of establishment, liberalization of internal borders and regional integration of the European Union – EU (under the umbrella of two political arrangements, namely intergovernance and supranationality) shaped the relations between member countries (which ceded part of their sovereignty) and communities (4) as well as between them and third country nationals entering the EU territory.

The way otherness has been thought out, managed, and integrated (1)- beginning with the gradual abolition of borders, within the Schengen territory (Agreement: 1985) and then, within the territory of the European Union (Amsterdam Treaty: 1997)- reflects the principles, the conditions, and the feelings to which the internal cohesion of the Union's social fabric has been handed over (6).

The border demarcation line – and, by extension, the criteria and rules followed to draw it – establishes an inclusion/exclusion relationship between internal and external elements with respect to it. On the one hand, internally, a sense of border has been built as a line that unites the "us" and the "other" and, on the other hand, externally, on the contrary, a sense of border has been built as a line that separates the "us" from the "other", drawing and regulating their relationship (6).

From free internal mobility to economic and political union (Lisbon Treaty: 2007), the pursuit for deep integration of member states has focused, within its borders, on economic leveling among member countries, on the values enshrined in the Treaties and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights including democracy, the rule of law, the freedoms of speech and religion, and the rights to equality and non-discrimination – the reasoning behind the creation of the "Promoting our European Way of Life" portfolio according to the European Commission (3).

Border challenges are optimized with the peak of migrant arrivals in the year 2015, when nearly one million people entered European territory. In addition to Syrians fleeing the war in their country, many immigrants, especially from African countries, were fleeing hunger and poverty. The arrival of this contingent has strained the challenges of distribution (equal conditions) and recognition (equal value) in all member states.

The EU's common migration policy deals with both voluntary migration – among them economic migrants – and forced migration – such as refugees. Since the signing of the Maastricht Treaty (1992), the EU has sought to regulate and restrain irregular immigration, based on cooperation processes between the countries involved in international migration, taking actions of a more global nature. Nevertheless, the management of the migration flow aimed at stabilizing bilateral relations between the concerned countries leads to the securitization of borders (3).

The organized institutional apparatus was the EU's answer to the security argument, based also on the fear of the collapse of the welfare state. With a focus on controlling migration flows and protecting the external border, decentralized agencies were created: European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex), involved in the management and control of external borders; the European Asylum Support Office (EASO), which assists in the implementation of member states' obligations under the asylum system; and the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol), which assists in law enforcement cooperation between member states, particularly in the field of migrant smuggling (3). In the European Commission's view, member states' asylum and migration policies, as a well-functioning management system, should underpin and complement integration policies.

Integration policy considers newly arrived (documented) migrants and EU citizens with migratory backgrounds typical of the diasporas of each member states. In the European Commission's view, ensuring effective integration and inclusion of migrants in the EU (with different socioeconomic conditions and labor market skills) is a social and economic investment because in addition to making European societies more cohesive, resilient, and prosperous, it may produce economic gains, including tax profits, contributions to national pension schemes, and national welfare in general (3). Nevertheless, as a supranational entity, the EU has no specific legal competence for integration policies, and it is up to the member states to define them.

FINDINGS

As far as the EU is concerned in key areas for integration of migrants and refugees, several measures have been taken in the last two decades (5), specifically in the years 2015 and 2016, when, according to European Commission data, there were 20 million third-country nationals residing in the EU, which represented 4 % of its total population (3).

In order to establish a common strategic framework that might help member states further develop and strengthen their national integration policies, the European Commission has published the first *European Action Plan on the Integration of Third-Country Nationals* (Jun/2016). Integration, as a multidimensional process, would cover several areas of intervention, at EU and member state level, based on the following policy priorities: pre-departure or pre-arrival measures (providing information and language skills); education; integration into the labor market and access to vocational training; access to basic services (housing, health) and active participation and social inclusion (2).

The 2016 Plan comprehended actions for each of the five policy priorities and for instruments for coordinating, financing, and monitoring it, briefly listing measures and the main actors of these measures. Although the local plans drawn up and the actions taken have made a positive contribution on improving the integration of third-country nationals in all EU member states, according to the Commission, some shortcomings and areas for improvement have emerged during their implementation. These include the lack of data and structured monitoring systems, and the difficulty of access to specific segments of the population (3).

The second *Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027* addresses cross-cutting issues such as promoting partnerships between key integration stakeholders, fighting racism and discrimination, optimizing the use and impact of EU funding on integration and inclusion, using digital tools and monitoring progress in delivering integration and inclusion policies based on reliable data. The Plan also considers the specific needs of different groups, among them, EU citizens with a migration background, women, religious minorities, and people with disabilities.

CONCLUSIONS

Within an innovative institutional arrangement, the EU has sought to address border challenges with measures to stem the flow of migration and Action Plans to integrate the immigrant population. Challenges linked to distribution (equal conditions) and recognition (equal value) in all member states proved themselves in the implementation of the 2016 Plan. In the drafting of the 2021-2027 Plan, in addition to third-country nationals, an attempt was made to ensure the integration and inclusion of EU citizens with a migration background as well as to emphasize the importance of the host society's involvement. Nevertheless, the biggest challenge for the EU is to dissociate the migration policy from the securitization that, besides reinforcing the argument of legal otherness (a line that ties the "us" and the "other"), strengthens the action against external migration flows, also feeding the identity border between the communitarian and the extra-communitarian (a line that separates the "us" from the "other"), thus limiting, to a great extent, the universalization of human rights.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The European Commission, after evaluating the 2016 Plan, made recommendations for the 2021-2027 Plan. Among other provisions, it indicates to improve the monitoring of integration results in the member states to measure progress and make necessary adjustments to policies and measures to increase their effectiveness. It also provides the rapidly transfer and replicate in other member states of those measures that have already proven successful at the national or regional level. The action plan recognizes the specific needs of certain categories and the possible intersections between migrant status and other segments of discrimination (e.g. gender, sexual orientation, age and disabilities). It reinforces in the plans the need to involve the host society and, more specifically, local communities. It also prioritizes the synergies between integration and other policies directly or indirectly relevant for migrants' integration, in particular access to housing, health services and new technologies (3).

REFERENCES

(1) BECKER, Luzia Costa. Globalização – Migração – Lusofonia: Novas dimensões na construção da alteridade in: Schmuck, Lydia & Corrêa, Marina (Hg./Eds.): Europa im Spiegel von Migration und Exil. Frank & Time GmVH, Berlim, 2015.

(2) COMISSÃO EUROPEIA. Comunicação ao Parlamento Europeu, ao Conselho, ao Comitê Econômico e Social Europeu e ao Comitê das Regiões. Plano de ação sobre a integração dos nacionais de países terceiros, 2016. Disponível em <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/PT/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52016DC0377>. Retrieved: 21/jul/2021.

(3) EUROPEAN COMMISSION. Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027 in Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions. Link disponível em https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/pdf/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf. Retrieved: 05/Jun/2021.

(4) LEITE, Ana Paula Moreira Rodrigues. O Complexo de Segurança na União Europeia: um estudo das implicações de segurança e defesa a partir da análise da crise de refugiados – Rio de Janeiro: IH/UFRJ, 2016.

(5) OLIVEIRA, Catarina Reis. Introdução. O desenvolvimento de planos de ação para a integração de imigrantes: Portugal e a Europa na última década in Planos de Integração para migrantes. Revista do Observatório das Migrações, N. 13, dezembro de 2016. Available at: <https://www.om.acm.gov.pt/publicacoes-om/revista-migracoes>. Acesso em 22/mai/2021.

(6) ROMIZI, Francesco. As políticas migratórias e suas matrizes étnicas in A mobilidade humana internacional: entre direitos ideais e políticas reais. Bettiol, Líria Maria et. al. [Orgs.] São Carlos: Pedro & João Editores, 2021.